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Antioxidant Activity of Ethanolic Extracts of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus*

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the antioxidant and antibacterial activities of some plants collected in Kien Giang province, Vietnam. The antioxidant property was determined for their antioxidant activity by DPPH, ABTS^{•+}, RP và TAC methods in vitro. The results showed that the ethanolic extract of *Artemisia vulgaris* displayed in vitro antioxidant activities with its IC₅₀ (half maximal inhibitory concentration) values of 734.323 µg/mL, 43.871 µg/mL, 185.32 µg/mL and 62.714 µg/mL, respectively. Antioxidant assay identified that, the ethanolic extract of *Costus speciosus* exhibited DPPH scavenging with IC₅₀ of 1158.24 µg/mL in comparison with the extract of *Pouzolzia zeylanica* expressing IC₅₀ at an amount of 1034.55 µg/mL. However, antioxidant capacity of *Costus speciosus* was approximately 2.85 times higher than that of *Pouzolzia zeylanica* in TAC method. Total phenolic and flavonoid contents of *Artemisia vulgaris* extract reached the highest at 103.8 mg GAE/g and 287.65 mg QE/g, respectively. These findings concluded that *Artemisia vulgaris* is a very potential herb containing natural antioxidant compounds.

Keywords: antioxidant, *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Costus speciosus*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica*

INTRODUCTION

Artemisia vulgaris, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* are known as traditional medicinal plants of Vietnamese people. The previous study showed that essential oils and plant extracts from *Artemisia vulgaris* have been applied in the treatment of human diseases thanks to its pharmacological activities of antiepileptic, antispasmodic, antiseptic, antibacterial, antimalarial, anticancer, hepatoprotective, diuretic, digestion (Cha *et al.*, 2007). *Artemisia vulgaris* contained phenolic, flavonoid, and terpenoid with antioxidants neutralizing free radicals, protecting the body from degenerative, cardiovascular and neurological diseases (Juvatkar *et al.*, 2012); whereas, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* presented many chemical compounds such as scopolin, scutellarein-7-O- α -L-rhamnoside, scopoletin, quercetin, quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucoside, apigenin, 2 α -hydroxyursolic acid (Fu *et al.*, 2012). At the same time, the methanol extract from this plant species demonstrated its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic effects (Hossain *et al.*, 2017). *Costus speciosus* showed its pharmacological effects of anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antidysuria, yellow urine treatment, anti-rheumatic, analgesic, antineuritic. The extract from *Costus speciosus* rhizome contained 2.12% of pure diosgenin, tigogenin, saponin and some triterpenes such as nocyloartanone, cycloartenol, cycloandenone (Dasgupta and Pandey, 1970; Gupta *et al.*, 1988). The results pointed up a diverse source of plant species with biologically active substances. In Viet Nam, there have been a limited numbers of studies on the antioxidant capacity of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* so far. In this study, the antioxidant activity was evaluated in order to find out the biochemical information of the three mentioned plants, forming the basis for further research aiming to create pharmaceutical chemical products for public health care.

MATERIALS

Plant materials and extracts

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Plant materials: Leaves of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* were collected in Kien Giang province. Plant specimens with accession numbers of KG-202017, KG-202018 and KG202019 respectively, were identified by Dr. Nguyen Thi Kim Hue (Department of Biology, College of Natural Sciences, Cantho university).

Methods and reagents applied in the study included DPPH (Sigma Aldrich, USA), methanol, ethanol, ABTS^{•+} (Sigma), quercetin, K₂S₂O₈, Folin-Ciocalteu, K₃Fe(CN)₆, Cl₃CCOOH, AlCl₃, NaNO₂ and other chemicals.

Plant extract preparation

2 kg of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* leaves was collected and rinsed with water. Plant materials was then shade dried at 50°C before grinding to make fine powder. After drying, the sample was placed in a cloth bag and soaked in ethanol 99°C. The extracts after maceration were collected and filtered through a filter paper. The crude ethanol extract was obtained by evaporating the solvent using a rotary evaporator. These resulting extracts were stored at 4°C.

Quantitative phenolic and flavonoid contents

The total of phenolic content was estimated by the method of Singleton *et al.* (1999). 0.5 mL of the extract was diluted in methanol. The reaction mixture was then shaken with a solution that included 2.5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu 10% and distilled water. After that, 2.5 mL of Na₂CO₃ 10% was added. The mixture was allowed to be incubated at 40°C for 30 min, and it gradually turned blue. The spectral absorbance of the mixture was measured at 765 nm. The data collected were expressed in mg of gallic acid equivalent per gram of sample extract (mg GAE/g extract).

The total of flavonoid content was determined according to the method described by Bag *et al.* (2015). 200 µL of extract was treated with ethanolic (500 µg/mL). The mixture was shaken vigorously after adding 200 µL of water and 40 µL of NaNO₂ 5%. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand for 5 min, followed by further adding 40 µL AlCl₃ 10% and shaking well. 400 µL NaOH 1 M and water were added to make up the volume of 1 mL after the reaction mixture was incubated for 6 min. The solution absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 510 nm. The data collected were expressed in mg of Quercetin equivalent per gram of sample extract (mg QE/g extract).

Evaluation of antioxidant activity

DPPH free radical scavenging: The antioxidant capacity of ethanol extracts was calculated as the description of Sharma *et al.* (2009). The reaction mixture which consisted of 100 µL of DPPH (6x10⁻⁴ M) and 100 µL of ethanol extract of *Artemisia vulgaris* (at the concentration of 125-1250 µg/mL), *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* (at the same concentration of 100- 1600 µg/mL) was incubated in the dark at room temperature for 60 min and the absorbance of DPPH was measured at 517 nm. The positive controls were commonly used in antioxidant assays such as gallic acid, BHA, quercetin, BHT, rutin, catechin, ascorbic acid, caffeic acid (Dave, 2009). Gallic acid was used as the standard in the current experiment and in other experiments as well.

ABTS^{•+} free radical scavenging efficiency: The free radical scavenging activity was identified according to the description of Nenadis *et al.* (2004). ABTS^{•+} solution was prepared by adding 2 mL of ABTS^{•+} solution (7 mM) to 2 mL of K₂S₂O₈ solution (2.45 mM). The solution was then incubated in the dark condition for 16h, followed by diluting with ethanol and adjusting the absorbance of the solution at 734 nm with a spectral density of 0.7±0.05. The ABTS^{•+} free radical scavenging activity was investigated by adding 990 µL ABTS^{•+} to 10 µL of the extract. The reaction mixture was incubated for 6 min. Then, the measurement of the spectral absorbance was carried out at 734 nm.

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Reducing power (RP): The reducing ability of a compound generally depends on the presence of reductants which have been exhibited antioxidative potential by breaking the free radical chain, donating a hydrogen atom (Saha *et al.*, 2008). In the study, the iron reducing power of ethanol extract was performed by the method of Padma *et al.* (2013). The reaction mixture was prepared by combining 0.5 mL extract, 0.5 mL phosphate buffer and 0.5 mL of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ 1%, respectively. After the reaction mixture was incubated at 50°C for 20 min, 0.5 mL of CCl_3COOH 10% was added, followed by centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 10 min. After centrifugation, 0.5 mL of the supernatant was collected and taken to mix with 0.5 mL of water and 0.1 mL of $FeCl_3$ 0.1%. The solution was then allowed to be shaken well. The spectral absorbance of the mixture was estimated at 700 nm.

Total antioxidant capacity (TAC): The experiment was carried out according to the method of Prieto *et al.* (1999). 100 μ L of the extract was treated with 1000 μ L of reagent solution (0.6 M sulfuric acid, 28 mM sodium phosphate, and 4 mM ammonium molybdate) to observe the reaction. The mixture was then covered and incubated at 95°C for 90 min. The absorbance of the solution after the reaction was measured at 695 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Total phenolic and flavonoid contents

The quantitative analysis results of total phenolic and flavonoid contents were displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Phenolic and flavonoid contents of the extracts

Quantitative method	<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i>	<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i>	<i>Costus speciosus</i>
TPC (mg GAE/g)	103.08 \pm 0.45	76.69 \pm 1.78	75.94 \pm 0.86
TFC (mg QE/g)	287.65 \pm 2.35	94.65 \pm 3.32	221.36 \pm 2.65

TPC: Total phenolic content (gallic acid equivalent mg/mL)

TFC: Total flavonoid content (quercetin equivalent μ g/mL)

The data in Table 1 pointed up the phenolic and flavonoid contents of ethanol extract of *Artemisia vulgaris* which were 103.08 mgGAE/g, 287.65 mgQE/g, respectively. The findings was higher than the methanol extract in the study of Erel *et al.* (2012) with the total flavonoid content of 67.98 \pm 6.65 mgGAE/g recorded. The result demonstrated that phenolic content also depended on the solvent used and the solvent concentration in extraction process. Similarly, the total phenolic content of ethanol extract of *Artemisia vulgaris* at 99° was also higher than that of the ethanol 70° in the study of Sunday and Roger (2015). Among the solvents used to extract phenolic, ethanol was considered to be the most commonly used solvent because of its safety and increased solubility of compounds from raw materials. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents of ethanol extract of *Pouzolzia zeylanica* collected were lower than that in the study of Li *et al.* (2011) with the value of 90.5 μ g/mL extracted in petroleum ether, but higher than that of Nguyen *et al.* (2018) with values of 38.68 mgGAE/g and 18.46 mgQE/g when extracted with ethanol 60°. Similarly, another study by Wang *et al.* (2018) reported that the phenolic and flavonoid contents of *Pouzolzia zeylanica* extracted in ethyl acetate solvent were 263.5 mgGAE/g and 388.3 mgQE/g, respectively, which was much higher than the data collected in this study. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents of *Costus speciosus* extract was higher than that of the study by Vijayalakshmi and Sarada (2008) which reported its total phenolic content of 11.45 mgGAE/g in leaves and 22.45 mgGAE/g in the stem.

The effect of DPPH radical scavenging activity

The free radical scavenging efficiency and antioxidant content equivalent to gallic acid (μ g/mL) were also calculated and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: DPPH free radical scavenging efficiency and gallic acid equivalents antioxidant content (μ g/ml) of the extracts

Extract	Content (μ g/ml)	DPPH free radical scavenging efficiency (%)	Gallic acid equivalents (μ g/ml)	IC ₅₀ value (μ g/mL)
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<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i>	125	5.955 ± 0.604 ^e	0.167 ± 0.038 ^e	734.323
	250	20.107 ± 0.830 ^d	1.486 ± 0.117 ^d	
	750	51.942 ± 1.726 ^c	4.454 ± 0.189 ^c	
	1000	71.842 ± 0.463 ^b	6.311 ± 0.058 ^b	
	1250	83.089 ± 1.445 ^a	7.359 ± 0.145 ^a	
<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i>	100	6.640 ± 1.188 ^e	0.742 ± 0.983 ^e	1034.55
	200	16.936 ± 1.026 ^d	1.646 ± 0.067 ^d	
	400	25.176 ± 3.973 ^c	2.371 ± 0.280 ^c	
	800	43.880 ± 5.289 ^b	4.014 ± 0.394 ^b	
	1600	73.376 ± 0.792 ^a	6.599 ± 0.093 ^a	
<i>Costus speciosus</i>	100	7.882 ± 0.8028 ^e	0.877 ± 0.073 ^e	1158.24
	200	15.869 ± 0.401 ^d	1.576 ± 0.038 ^d	
	400	21.961 ± 0.309 ^c	2.109 ± 0.033 ^c	
	800	41.005 ± 0.731 ^b	3.775 ± 0.068 ^b	
	1600	64.767 ± 0.766 ^a	5.854 ± 0.068 ^a	
Gallic acid				4.059

Different letters in superscript signify statistically significant differences from one another using Tukey's test ($p \leq 0.05$)

The results in Table 2 showed that, the gallic acid equivalents and the DPPH free radical scavenging efficiency were directly proportional to the concentration of the extract, which mean when the extract concentration increased, the gallic acid equivalent content also increased. As shown in Table 2, the *Artemisia vulgaris* extract presented an increase of antioxidant content from 0.167 to 7.359 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and the DPPH free radical scavenging efficiency increased from 5.955% to 83.089% at the extract concentration of 125-1250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. *Pouzolzia zeylanica* extract increased from 0.742 to 6.599 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at the same time of the increase of the efficiency from 6.640% to 73.376%. *Costus speciosus* extract showed its free radical scavenging efficiency increased from 7.882 to 64.767% with the equivalents content increased from 0.877 to 5.854 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The result also determined that IC_{50} values of the three extracts obtained were much lower than that of gallic acid standard ($\text{IC}_{50} = 4.059 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Compared with gallic acid, the ethanol extract of *Artemisia vulgaris* was 180.91 times lower ($\text{IC}_{50} = 734.323 \mu\text{g/mL}$), the extract of *Pouzolzia zeylanica* was 254.87 times lower ($\text{IC}_{50} = 1034.55 \mu\text{g/mL}$), and the extract of *Costus speciosus* was 285.35 times lower. ($\text{IC}_{50} = 1158.24$). Thus, the DPPH free radical scavenging efficiency of the extracts was ranked in the order of the greatest to the smallest that were *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Costus speciosus* and *Pouzolzia zeylanica*, respectively. In general, among the three medicinal species, *Artemisia vulgaris* had higher DPPH free radical scavenging activity because of its low IC_{50} value. Although applied the same method of DPPH, *Artemisia vulgaris* extract had a lower free radical scavenging ability compared with the study of Sunday and Roger (2015) which had an IC_{50} value of 976 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and the study of Erel *et al.* (2012) having an IC_{50} value of 114 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Similarly, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* which was extracted using ethyl acetate solvent showed its lower IC_{50} value than the study of Anh *et al.* (2017) with $\text{IC}_{50} = 50.71 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and the study of Wang *et al.* (2018) with the IC_{50} value of 47.12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. *Costus speciosus* extract had much lower effect on free radical neutralization than that of the study by Nehete *et al.* (2010) with the IC_{50} of 14.26 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and the study of Vijayalakshmi and Sarada (2008) with the IC_{50} of 139 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

ABTS^{•+} free radical scavenging efficiency

The ABTS^{•+} free radical scavenging efficiency of the extracts and the standard was presented through the IC_{50} value derived from the corresponding linear regression equation, the results were presented in Table 3.

Bảng 3: Phương trình hồi quy tuyến tính và giá trị IC_{50}

Sample	Linear regression equation	IC_{50} ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Acid gallic	$y = 90.13x + 5.005$	0.500 ± 0.001
<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> extract	$y = 1.077x + 2.750$	43.871 ± 0.077
<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i> extract	$y = 0.751x - 2.545$	91.694 ± 1.001
<i>Costus speciosus</i> extract	$y = 0.355x + 3.779$	130.077 ± 0.329

The results figured out that the ability to neutralize ABTS^{•+} free radicals of the three extracts was lower than that of gallic acid. *Artemisia vulgaris* extract ($\text{IC}_{50} = 43.871 \mu\text{g/mL}$), *Pouzolzia zeylanica* extract ($\text{IC}_{50} = 91,694 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and *Costus speciosus* extract ($\text{IC}_{50} = 130.077 \mu\text{g/mL}$) showed a statistically significant

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difference at 5% compared with gallic acid ($IC_{50} = 0.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$) in the ability to neutralize other $ABTS^{\bullet+}$ free radicals. *Costus speciosus* extract displayed its lower efficiency in neutralizing $ABTS^{\bullet+}$ free radicals compared with its methanol extract in the study of Vijayalakshmi and Sarada (2008) with IC_{50} of $85.51 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Based on the research results, the $ABTS^{\bullet+}$ free radical neutralization effect of *Artemisia vulgaris* extract played the highest, but still 87.74 times lower than that of gallic acid.

Free radical scavenging efficiency according to RP and TAC assays

The antioxidative effect of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus*, based on the iron reduction capacity was calculated as equivalent to the concentration of gallic acid ($\mu\text{g/mL}$). The IC_{50} value was used for comparison because the higher the absorbance, the stronger the reducing power. The study results on the neutralization efficiency basing on the iron and phosphomolybdenum reduction capacity were shown in Figure 1.

The results showed that the iron-reducing capacity (RP) of the extracts of *Artemisia vulgaris* ($IC_{50} = 185.32 \mu\text{g/mL}$), *Pouzolzia zeylanica* ($IC_{50} = 1196.47 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and *Costus speciosus* ($IC_{50} = 1011.87 \mu\text{g/mL}$) was lower than that of gallic acid ($IC_{50} = 10.460 \mu\text{g/mL}$) at 17.72 times, 114.38 times and 96.73 times, respectively. From the above results, the iron-reducing capacity of the extracts was ranked in the order of the highest to the smallest which were *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Costus speciosus*, and *Pouzolzia zeylanica*, respectively - *Artemisia vulgaris* extract with a IC_{50} value lower than $200 \mu\text{g/mL}$. However, the *Pouzolzia zeylanica* which was extracted using ethyl acetate solvent had lower iron reduction capacity than that in the study of Wang *et al.* (2018) with the IC_{50} of $4.35 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and the study of Nguyen *et al.* (2018) with the IC_{50} of $4.35 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Ethyl acetate is a solvent that can extract more biologically active components than ethanol. Therefore the antioxidant activity presents higher. Previous research has demonstrated that flavonoids were the compound with strong antioxidant activity. In this experiment, the results demonstrated that the flavonoid content in *Artemisia vulgaris* and *Costus speciosus* extracts was the highest (Table 1). The results of this study were completely consistent with previous studies.

Figure 1: IC_{50} values for antioxidant activity of plant extracts using RP and TAC assay

The ability to de-complex Mo of the extracts had lower IC_{50} values compared with the IC_{50} value of gallic acid. Specifically, *Artemisia vulgaris* extract was 2.52 times lower, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* extract was 10.34 times lower and *Costus speciosus* extract was 3.62 times lower than that of gallic acid. The above results concluded that the Phosphomolybdenum reduction capacity of the extracts was ranked in the order of *Artemisia vulgaris* extract to *Costus speciosus* and *Pouzolzia zeylanica*, respectively, with *Artemisia vulgaris* and *Costus speciosus* having IC_{50} values lower than $200 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Among all the extracts analyzed, a

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significant phenolic content and antioxidant activity were found for *Artemisia vulgaris* extract so it can be predicted that the antioxidant activity may be due to the total phenolic content in the plant. Previously it was revealed that the antioxidant activity of phenolic is mainly due to their redox properties, which allow them to act as reducing agents, hydrogen donors, and singlet oxygen quenchers (Macheix and Fleuriot, 2018).

The study results showed that the antioxidant ability of the extracts of the *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* were lower than that of the *Artemisia vulgaris* extract in all four antioxidant methods. However, there was a small difference that *Pouzolzia zeylanica* extract had higher DPPH and ABTS^{•+} free radical but iron and Phosphomolybdenum reduction capacity in neutralization efficiency than that of the *Costus speciosus* extract. Significant correlations were found between the total phenolic content of *Pouzolzia zeylanica* extract (76.69 mg GAE/g) and the neutralizing effect of DPPH, ABTS^{•+}, and the total flavonoid content of the *Costus speciosus* extract (221.36 mg QE/g) with the ability to reduce iron and Phosphomolybdenum. Therefore, it can be assumed that flavonoids and phenolic are the main antioxidant compounds in many plant species.

CONCLUSION

Research on the antioxidant capacity of ethanol extracts of *Artemisia vulgaris*, *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* showed the antioxidant potential of these plant species. By using different antioxidant assay methods in research including DPPH, ABTS^{•+}, iron and Phosphomolybdenum reduction capacity, the results demonstrated that *Artemisia vulgaris* exhibited very good antioxidant activity with its lower values of IC₅₀ compared with *Pouzolzia zeylanica* and *Costus speciosus* of 734.323 ± 19.952 , 43.871 ± 0.077 , 185.32 ± 0.330 , 62.714 ± 0.143 µg/mL, respectively. This result was also consistent with the quantitative results of phenolic and flavonoid compounds (103.08 mg GAE/g and 287.65 mg QE/g). The study pointed up the antioxidant activity of the three common plant species used in daily meals of Vietnamese people and determined that this is one of the potential plant species for human disease prevention and treatment.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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